

Workshop: Positive Design. Designing the road of happiness

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Topic *“If you want to increase your happiness, don’t buy new products, change your behaviour.”* Positive psychologists sometimes advise that not too much ought to be expected from the contributions to subjective well-being made by consumer products (Nicolao, Irwin, & Goodman, 2009). The ‘Positive Design’ workshop challenges this view by proposing that design can increase happiness. The central question addressed is: How can design contribute to human flourishing? Positive Design is an umbrella term for all forms of design, design research and design intention in which explicit attention is paid to the effects of design on the subjective well-being of individuals and communities (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013; Pohlmeier & Desmet, 2014). In their workshop, Anna and Pieter will introduce their view on Positive Design and present examples of how design can help people in finding balance between pleasure, purpose in life, and virtuous behaviour. They will introduce some of the key research questions in the domain of Positive Design and detail a Positive Design Framework in-depth. In addition to providing relevant background knowledge, a number of hands-on exercises will be conducted to familiarize participants with essential concepts and design methods. The aim of the workshop is to inform, engage, and inspire; offering a balance between theory & research on the one hand, and experiences & design examples on the other.

Keywords *Design for human values, Design for well-being, Theoretical foundations of design and emotion*